

Union 5G

From E-Pandemic Management to the EU's Digital Overhaul

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Abstract. In this paper, global E-Pandemic Management is seen as an opportunity to advance digitalization in the EU (European Union) in all areas, such as E-Education, E-Health, E-Administration, E-Climate Protection, or E-Economy. For a functioning E-Pandemic Management, the digitalization of the affected states, i.e. the process-controlled use of IT (Information Technology) in all areas, is virtually a prerequisite. Therefore, we can also talk about IT-supported pandemic management or IT-supported education instead of talking about E-Pandemic Management or E-Education. We will explain E-Pandemic Management using a directed process for the execution of digitalization projects, which is divided into the sections Motivation, Basics, Modeling, Tool Support, Solution, Usage, and Summary with Outlook. The overarching motto here is that the digital world induces and monitors the analog world. Digitization has the primary effect of making people's lives in the analog world more accurate through process-centric modeling and more secure, because it is now also supported from the digital world by the models (schemas) that have been implemented. However, this holistic approach is only physical possible in the analog world based on a hybrid cloud computing architecture and the 5G mobile communications standard that has already been installed in many places.

Keywords. Pandemic Management · Cloud Computing · Cloud Platform · 5G Standard · Repository System

1 Motivation

On March 11, 2020, the WHO (World Health Organization) declares a worldwide pandemic due to the rapid spread of the Coronavirus. This has the consequence that in almost all countries very far-reaching measures are enforced in the public and private sector, which represent a high restriction of the previously accustomed life [30]. These

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measures such as contact restrictions, curfews and quarantine orders, fall under the so-called pandemic and contact management, which are among the most important methods for getting a pandemic under control and restoring normal life [17]. Besides, there are digital or IT-based solutions, such as the Corona Tracing App or the RKI's (Robert Koch-Institute) Data Donation App, which are designed to support Pandemic Management digitally [1, 27]. For optimal pandemic response, all stakeholders should work together efficiently, which in reality looks different. The pandemic represents a worldwide phenomenon - but the handling and management of it are handled in a highly differentiated manner: different political approaches, different process-oriented approaches, as well as different IT-supported approaches, exist [9]. Even at the national level, there is no consensus. There is a lack of uniform digitization and a consistent system that allows all-encompassing networking [28]. This fact poses a real problem for efficient pandemic control and indicates that progress can only be achieved by taking the next step of digitalization. Besides E-Pandemic Management itself, the application domains of E-Education, E-Health and E-Economy are also affected, to which E-Pandemic Management can be subordinated [12]. The goal is to use a hybrid cloud computing-based platform solution to circumvent the problems mentioned and to enable optimized and digital pandemic management from the cloud using interactive application systems. Moreover, it is a generic solution that is not limited to the current pandemic and can be extended and used in the future. Finally, it is also important to note that the development and achievement must be guided by the "language critical EU digitization" guardrails: Process-driven interactive application systems as a contemporary application system type, an integrative architecture to support the analog through the digital world, and language-competent citizens empowered to communicate and cooperate in a language-critical, IT-supported manner, which is made possible by language-based informatics and the existing method of language criticism [21, 22].

2 Basics

For a better understanding and an easier classification of the topic in the overall context, the most necessary basics are briefly conveyed within this chapter. The chapter is divided into the technical (digital world) and expert (analog world) areas. Thus the actual target functionality becomes recognizable: The digital world causes and supervises the analog world via interactive application systems [21, 22]. The digital world follows the laws of formal logic and thus the laws of "being true" according to Frege. While the analog world is based on the laws of nature and empiricism and often also on the laws of "accept true" (belief, opinion, knowledge) [23].

2.1 Expert area

Here, as described, the professionally relevant basics of the analog world are presented.

Pandemic. A pandemic is a disease that, compared to other diseases, spreads very quickly over wide areas, such as countries and continents. In the worst case, a pandemic can lead to the disintegration of the functioning of all public and private structures, to an overload and thus to high death rates among the population. To avoid such proportions, it is essential to develop appropriate planning and preparation for such situations [26, 31].

Pandemic Management. To be able to control a pandemic, sophisticated management is required: the pandemic management. The goal is to ensure the functioning and maintenance of public functions, companies, the structure of society and essential structures in the event of a pandemic or crisis. Overall, well-thought-out pandemic management should be divided into different phases. The behavior between pandemics as well as before, during and after a pandemic must be planned. A particularly important component in this context is contact person management, in which contact persons (those who have come into contact with the disease) are to be managed [14].

E-Pandemic Management. According to Götz, the term E-Pandemic Management is understood to mean an "IT-supported application that performs tasks relating to the preview and planning, organization, management, coordination or control of a pandemic [...]" [12]. At the same time, following Götz, the term is subordinated to E-Economy and E-Education, which in turn are subordinated to E-Health. E-Pandemic Management is thus also the context to be digitized. To achieve the target function the prerequisite is optimal process-centric digitization, i.e. IT use here, in the entire area - E-Pandemic Management, E-Health, E-Education, E-Economy [12].

Stakeholders. Various stakeholders are involved in pandemic management. For a simplified understanding, the following **Fig. 1.** Parties involved in Pandemic Management illustrates their interrelationship. These include the health authorities, which are primarily responsible for contact person management [11], the government, which acts as coordinator and regulator [4], but also the media and social networks play a decisive role in terms of information and knowledge management. Not to be neglected are also the citizens themselves, who have a very great responsibility during a pandemic and must behave within society in a manner appropriate to the situation [8, 13].

Fig. 1. Parties involved in Pandemic Management

2.2 Technical

Here, the technically relevant basics of the digital world are presented as described.

Cloud. The term "cloud" refers to a potentially worldwide network. A cloud does not represent a physical size, but rather a digital ecosystem consisting of remote servers, which can be distributed all over the world. These make various tasks possible, as is also the case with classic structures: data storage, data management or the provision of services. In principle, the different approaches to the topic of cloud must be mentioned: the public, private, hybrid and community cloud. These types differ mainly in the extent to which persons or institutions can/are allowed to access the services of the respective cloud [3, 18].

Cloud Computing. The term cloud computing refers to this collection of services, applications or resources that are available to all users simply, flexibly and at low cost - in short, a repository. Besides, it is not necessary to have IT expertise to use such offerings. The provider is responsible for operation and maintenance, and the user merely pays a usage fee [25].

Cloud Platform. A cloud platform is nothing more than a Repository System in the cloud, which is a directory of services etc. A user can see which services can be executed via the platform, but not how they work, which is not necessary for principle [3].

5G Standard. The term 5G refers to the latest generation of mobile communications standards, which is establishing itself worldwide as the standard for the mobile Internet - during a great deal of competition (political, technological, ecological, etc.). At the same time the 5G network represents a successor to the existing 4G standard. The advancing expansion of the new standard will enable a wide variety of areas of life to benefit further from digitalization. Since data exchange is faster than with LTE, a much faster exchange of data is being pushed [19, 24].

3 Modeling

The beginnings of modeling can be found in different subfields (e.g. databases and programming) of computer science. Here, the decisive question is about the content, formal and technical meaning of the data. "In this context, data are statements about information objects and their properties based on concepts." [20] In the context of modeling, processes are modeled in this case with BPMN 2.0 diagrams, as directed sequences of an occurrence [23]. Especially since this is possible in different modeling domains. In the context of pandemic management different processes of the overall process were considered for this purpose. It is particularly important to mention that a modeling approach established by Volker Stiehl [29] according to the Process-driven Architecture is chosen at this point: first, the domain-oriented expert-view of processes is modeled (which is done in this chapter). In Chapter 5, the solution, the technically relevant view is then focused on.

Fig. 2. Business Process of an immunization administration

The upper process (Fig. 2) shows the domain-specific business process of an immunization administration. If a change in the vaccination strategy takes place, the citizens managed in two lists (one list for citizens who were not eligible for vaccination according to the old vaccination strategy and a second list with citizens waiting for an appointment) must be checked again for vaccination eligibility according to the new strategy. The verification is performed per citizen according to the new vaccination strategy and, depending on the verification result, results in the dispatch of a vaccination appointment, entry in the list of waiting citizens or in the list of non-vaccination-eligible citizens. To accomplish its task, the process relies on notification of an immunization strategy change, as indicated in the model by the service contract. Through the service contract, process-driven applications express their requirements for services to be provided

externally. How this contract is implemented in concrete terms is not of interest to the process of the process-driven application and is part of the technical implementation of Chapter 5.

Besides, the same approach was followed for the following basic pandemic management processes: Suspicion of contact, suspicion when symptoms are present, data monitoring by the health department and statistical use of anonymous aggregated data.

4 Tool support

By the realization of different analog-digital converters (e.g. first electron tube by Konrad Zuse) the time of computer science begins and finds a provisional end utilizing an optimal software architecture (e.g. the language-stepped multi-purpose architecture, i. A. Gottlob Frege), which was specified and regulates the transition in a contradiction-free way between the analog and digital world, language-logically [23]. The analog-digital converter in technology corresponds to the emotion-speech act converter in humans. What electronic chips are in technology, concepts are in humans [10]. The function of the chips in technology is taken over in humans by the concepts, more precisely: their physical representation, the cells, in the brains. Human-centered symbol manipulation, researched according to Ernst Cassirer [5–7], is the basis for a new language pedagogy that ensures a more understanding interaction of users with information technology (e.g. smartphones, computers). In the future, all further developments should be based on this basic architecture (**Fig. 3**) and interdisciplinary, with the basis of a philosophy of science [15] that is IT-supported, leading to ever newer results in research, which will enter in ever better IT-supported application solutions. These are then mostly interactive application systems that want to satisfy the Turing ideal and at the same time, on the human side, assume free speech acts according to Ernst Cassirer "Animal symbolicum" as the basis of reasoning [5–7]. The multi-purpose architecture mentioned is illustrated in the following **Fig. 3** for the domain of E-Pandemic Management. As mentioned, this architecture can be applied to a wide variety of domains; E-Pandemic Management can easily be replaced by other domains (e.g. E-Climate Management).

Fig. 3. Integrative General Purpose Architecture [23]

Especially in this context of E-Pandemic Management, different tools are used, which in turn can be classified in the architecture. The chapter is mainly based on cloud computing technology, using the Google Cloud Platform as an example, from which a wide variety of services and technologies are used in this context.

Cloud Computing. To enable a more efficient data flow for pandemic management, it seems sensible to establish a cloud platform that enables and partially takes over the management and processing of the data. In this context, the deployment options (private, public, hybrid, community, etc.) must be considered and used in a targeted manner. In the case of Pandemic Management, a hybrid cloud solution is particularly useful: For example, it may make sense for each office to have its private cloud to organize the administration, but for the offices to be connected to form a community cloud to enable the entire pandemic management between the actors via the cloud. At the same time, the users must also be able to participate in the system, which means that there must also be a public cloud aspect so that appropriate interaction by the citizen can take place. Also, a wide variety of services should be considered, which further leads to increase efficiency. Google offers a total of over a hundred services in various categories, from storage to networking, big data and security [2].

Mobile application based on a user repository. With the help of an interactive application system, which is also based on a repository-supported architecture that is used by citizens, the offices are supported in contact tracking with the help of a digital approach. The focus is on the user and their ability to manage their identity and the data themselves. The user is also offered further opportunities to contribute directly to efficient contact management in a digital way (e.g. in the form of digital diaries that can be automatically forwarded to offices) [12].

Progressive Webapp. A progressive web app also represents one of the mentioned interfaces to the cloud. Especially for the stakeholders such as the health departments, physicians, laboratories and other institutions, it makes sense to use the web interface, since here often also several information from the cloud must be displayed or fed at once. Through this web-based interface, the basic interaction with the cloud platform is made possible for the various user groups [16].

5 Solution

This chapter presents a potential solution approach based on the previous expert modeling and tool support to create a cloud computing-based solution for E-Pandemic Management. The focus is on the implementation using the service contract implementation layer of the process-driven architecture. The solution corresponds to the integrative BPMN schema, which includes the technical layer [29].

The service of notification of a change in vaccination strategy expected in the business process of the process-driven application and described via the service contract must now be implemented in concrete terms, which is why this level (see **Fig. 2**) is referred to as the service contract implementation layer. This layer now takes over the coordination of external information sources and evaluates this information, e.g., using artificial intelligence. If this evaluation results in an urgently required change of strategy, this is indicated via a message to the process-driven application. The service contract implementation layer thus fulfills the required service contract.

As already described in the modeling chapter this step was also carried out for the remaining processes. The digitization of further processes relating to the pandemic will also affect other e-areas. An E-EU can gradually be achieved in this way. As explained at the beginning Corona is a worldwide pandemic, which means that pandemic management is also required worldwide [9, 29]. As in Germany, there are different approaches to this management. This makes it clear that it may make sense to scale the concept developed here further and not just to manage it at the federal or national level, but ultimately to expand it nationally or even internationally. As the following **Fig. 4** shows, the processes at lower levels flow into the processes at higher levels. To approach digitization in a solution-oriented manner the principle of top-down coordination/bottom-up development should be followed [21, 22]. The concept presented should therefore be coordinated from the top, but developed by lower levels and then scaled up. Digitalization based on the cloud platform in particular can open up the possibility of integrating many countries into the system. Since resources and services are used entirely from the cloud, upscaling is possible without any other difficulties.

Fig. 4. New EU – through-digitized [14]

Furthermore, the presented approach enables a special degree of user-orientation. Since in the foreseeable future humans (regardless of their age or IQ (Intelligence Quotient)) will in all likelihood no longer forget anything crucial and will always be provided with the highest quality knowledge for making decisions or performing actions, regardless of when or where they need it, an adequate tool is also required here. Thus, an approach is delivered with which people can manage their schemata and their knowledge better and convert them into actions [23].

6 Usage

Especially in the 21st century, data represent a huge potential and can even be considered the "oil of the century". However, it is important here that schemes for interpreting this "raw material" - knowledge and information management thus play an important role [23]. It is often the case that we cannot do anything with the knowledge we have and it is difficult to distinguish whether we believe, mean or know something. Just the use of knowledge must be coordinated by appropriate management concerning the use in a community for the achievement of progress. At the current time, we have a wide variety of apps and services available to support us in this (e.g. Blinkist or Wikipedia). The goal must be to constantly adapt the schemata of our reality orientation - dialogically if possible - to changing circumstances. Ideally, this adaptation should be co-acted by different scientific disciplines, since schemata only represent the language-logical supports in an analogous world. Through this background also the use in this context and its data should be represented. For decades, the function of information and knowledge management has been assumed by so-called Chief Information Officers in companies and the state.

7 Summary with outlook

The concept of cloud computing supported pandemic management described in this paper has the potential to address the problems mentioned at the beginning and enable more efficient management of pandemics that require contact tracking. A language-critical digitization and education of users to use languages in a disciplined manner as a condition emerges, bring all the components described closer together. With renewed reference to the guardrails of EU digitization, the educational level of the population and its language competence is supported by technology. In this context, digitization represents the logic-based part of enlightenment. At the same time a multi-purpose software architecture between the digital world (cloud computing) and the analog world processes has to be built and interactive application systems developed according to the Volker-Stiehl method have to be established. The digital world thus supports the described things and events from the analog world using the formal-logical laws. Digitization in itself thus means the education of people from the analog world to a disciplined use of language. On the hardware technology side, the focus is also on the 5G standard. The resulting networking of all participants thus represents an essential added value. In addition to illustrating an efficient solution for E-Pandemic Management, the concept can also be seen as a critique of current inefficient and non-digital attempts at pandemic management. The applied digitization step can create a central cloud-based platform that can be flexibly and easily extended by different modules and features depending on the use case. Nevertheless, it must be noted at this point that the system developed here is to some extent dependent on how willing the user is per se to release his data in the first place. Since the current Corona pandemic is a worldwide problem, there is an international and worldwide case for top-down coordination and bottom-up expansion or development of this concept. However, this will require appropriate centers to take up the coordination of such large-scale digitization projects in the future. In the future, there is also the possibility of expanding the concept and applying it to other phenomena - e.g. E-Climate protection or the E-Economy. Using an actual implementation of this concept, it will be achieved that the digital world is connected to the analog world via interactive application systems and the "educated citizen" and that a language-driven digitization and education of users to a disciplined use of language can take place.

Finally, it should be noted that for the successful implementation of such a concept a suitable infrastructure must be in place concerning cloud computing and the 5G mobile network - neither of which is yet the case in Germany. This also applies to digitization, applications and E-Education for the population. All of these areas still leave a lot of room for improvement compared with countries such as Israel. The motto now is: see how things are and do better than dictatorial states.

8 Glossary

E. The acronym "E" (e.g. in E-Pandemic Management) is derived from "electronic data processing" (EDP) and is used in the sense of "EDP-supported". A synonymous term

would also be "information technology-supported" or "IT-supported pandemic management."

Interactive Application System. Any information technology (IT)-associated object - to the extent that it is in the use of (language-enabled) humans or their actions - is an interactive application system, and its intercommunicating functioning depends critically on language mastery - on the part of both humans and technology.

Repository. A repository (plural: repositories) is a self-managing directory for storing and describing digital objects for a digital archive (e.g., database, program library). The described objects are usually not stored in the repositories.

References

1. (2020) Open-Source Project Corona-Warn-App. <https://www.corona-warn.app/en/>. Accessed 20 May 2021
2. Ballnath E (2019) Einführung in die Google Cloud, die Cloud Services, Cloud Security, AI und Machine Learning. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BO1Z2IYs2iU>
3. Bitkom (ed) (2009) Cloud Computing - Evolution in der Technik, Revolution im Business. Bitkom-Leitfaden
4. Bornermann B, Christen M (2020) Verantwortung und Rolle des nachhaltigen Staats
5. Cassirer E (2010) Philosophie der symbolischen Formen. Erster Teil: Die Sprache. Philosophische Bibliothek, vol 607. Meiner, Hamburg
6. Cassirer E, Rosenkranz C (2010) Philosophie der symbolischen Formen. Zweiter Teil: Das mythische Denken. Philosophische Bibliothek, vol 608. Meiner, Hamburg
7. Cassirer E, Clemens J, Rosenkranz C (2010) Philosophie der symbolischen Formen. Dritter Teil: Phänomenologie der Erkenntnis. Philosophische Bibliothek, vol 609. Felix Meiner Verlag, Hamburg
8. Chuang Y-C, Huang Y-L, Tseng K-C et al. (2015) Social capital and health-protective behavior intentions in an influenza pandemic. PLoS One 10:e0122970. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0122970
9. Feld L, Truger A, Wieland V (2020) Die gesamtwirtschaftliche Lage angesichts der Corona-Pandemie
10. Frege G (2008) Funktion, Begriff, Bedeutung, 1. Aufl., Textausg. Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, Göttingen
11. Gostomzyk J (2021) COVID-19-Pandemie – eine sozialmedizinische Betrachtung. Public Health Forum 29:8–10. doi: 10.1515/pubhef-2020-0129
12. Götz M (2020) E-Pandemiemanagement: Verteilte Lösung mit einer Repository-gestützten Architektur

13. Kapitza T, Greiff F-H, Mann K (2020) Das Gesundheitssystem in der Post-COVID-19-Epoche – Die Pandemiekrise und neue Wege des Pandemiemanagements. MWV Medizinisch Wissenschaftliche Verlagsgesellschaft
14. Koch-Institut R (2017) Nationaler Pandemieplan Teil I. doi: 10.25646/112
15. Lorenzen P (2011) Constructive philosophy. University of Massachusetts Press, Amherst, Mass
16. Majchrzak TA, Biørn-Hansen A, Grønli T-M Progressive Web Apps: the Definite Approach to Cross-Platform Development?
17. Mayr V, Nußbaumer-Streit B, Gartlehner G (2020) Quarantäne alleine oder in Kombination mit weiteren Public-Health-Maßnahmen zur Eindämmung der COVID-19 Pandemie: Ein Cochrane Rapid Review (Quarantine Alone or in Combination with Other Public Health Measures to Control COVID-19: A Rapid Review (Review)). Gesundheitswesen 82:501–506. doi: 10.1055/a-1164-6611
18. Mell P, Grance T (2011) The NIST Definition of Cloud Computing
19. Monserrat JF, Mange G, Braun V et al. (2015) METIS research advances towards the 5G mobile and wireless system definition. J Wireless Com Network 2015:26. doi: 10.1186/s13638-015-0302-9
20. Ortner E (1997) Methodenneutraler Fachentwurf. Zu den Grundlagen einer anwendungsorientierten Informatik. Teubner-Reihe Wirtschaftsinformatik. Teubner, Stuttgart, Leipzig
21. Ortner E (1999) Repository Systems. Teil 1: Mehrstufigkeit und Entwicklungsumgebung. Informatik-Spektrum 22:235–251. doi: 10.1007/s002870050141
22. Ortner E (1999) Repository Systems. Teil 2: Aufbau und Betrieb eines Entwicklungsrepositoriums. Informatik Spektrum 22:351–363. doi: 10.1007/s002870050164
23. Ortner E (2005) Sprachbasierte Informatik. Wie man mit Wörtern die Cyber-Welt bewegt. Eagle Eagle-Lecture, vol 25. Ed. am Gutenbergplatz, Leipzig
24. Patel S, Chauhan M, Kapadiya K (2012) 5G: Future Mobile Technology-Vision 2020
25. Repschläger, Pannicke, Zarnekow (2010) Cloud Computing: Definitionen, Geschäftsmodelle und Entwicklungspotenziale
26. RKI (2009) Was ist eine Pandemie? <https://www.rki.de/Shared-Docs/FAQ/Pandemie/FAQ18.html>
27. RKI (2020) Corona-Datenspende | Robert Koch-Institut - Corona-Datenspende. <https://corona-datenspende.de/>. Accessed 20 May 2021
28. Spilker I (2020) Kontaktpersonen digital und effizient nachverfolgen. <https://www.helmholtz.de/gesundheit/kontaktpersonen-digital-und-effizient-nachverfolgen/>
29. Stiehl V (2014) Process-driven applications with BPMN. Springer, Cham
30. WHO (2020) Pandemie der Coronavirus-Krankheit (COVID-19). <https://www.euro.who.int/de/health-topics/health-emergencies/coronavirus-covid-19/novel-coronavirus-2019-ncov>

31. World Health Organization (2005) WHO global influenza preparedness plan. The role of The Role of WHO and recommendations for national measures before and during pandemics.